
Analysis of Student's Perception of Teacher Humor in EFL Classroom

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on students' perceptions of the teacher humor given in English classroom. The purpose this research is to find out how, the type of humor given, as well as to analyze students' perceptions of the humor given by the teacher in English classroom. This research was conducted using thematic analysis tools. Students are given several questions in which the questions depend on variations in student answers. Informants of this study amounted to 4 people. Based on the statements submitted by the informants, it is known that their English teacher uses question and answer as a means of providing humor in the class. Some of them also said that the teacher can be someone who provokes the anxiety of his students, in which the student's anxiety can become a separate humor in the class. According to them too, there are positive and negative benefits by providing humor in the classroom. One of the positive benefits is that they can easily remember the learning material that is being studied together, while one of the negative benefits is that there are some students who do not respect their teacher in class.

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INTRODUCTION

The teacher's communication skills can show their humorous nature. It aims to make students comfortable with the delivery of material carried out by the teacher. According to Imamah (2019) students can give full attention to the material presented by the teacher if the learning atmosphere is comfortable. As a teacher, being friends with students is finding the best way to get more attention and can also encourage students' willingness to learn. Likewise Ocon (2015) stated that are more preferable to a professor who have their sense of humor. Classes without humor will feel very boring and will not attract students' attention to study. Therefore, the use of humor in the classroom is one step that can reduce the pressure that exists in the classroom when learning activities are taking place.

A pleasant atmosphere can make the class less tense. Tension in the classroom will make students feel uncomfortable to carry out learning activities. The ability to manage classrooms through humor is one of the activities that can reduce students' stress levels. Humor is a way of communicating by triggering stimuli where these stimuli will reflexively trigger someone to laugh (Sinulingga, 2022). Humor is basically something that can be enjoyed by various groups, no matter young or old, rich or poor, everyone can enjoy it (Labibah, 2022). Therefore, humor is something that can strengthen the relationship between each individual. Even so, humor for children with humor for adults is something that must be considered in the

delivery previous research conducted by Knowles (2021) states that humor is something that teachers must give to their students during learning activities. In addition to these points, humor has several other useful points, among them are; (1) Lowering affective filter; (2) Attention to form; (3) Memory; (4) Communicative competence; and (5) Humor as coping mechanism.

Teachers who cannot make the atmosphere comfortable will make students judge the class is a scary class and the teacher will get the title of saturation so that it will affect the students' psyche and attention (Wamin, 2020). According to David Krech and Richard S. Crutchfield (cited in Shambodo (2020), states that perception will not occur without an external influence from an individual, the factors that influence perception include; (1) Functional factors; (2) Personal factors; (3) Situational factors; and (4) Structural factors.

Functional Factors

This factor serves as a reference material for a person in appreciating the stimulus he receives. This factor is personal, therefore, each individual will judge something differently from others based on experience, views, personality, and other things that are subjective. In this functional factor, it can be said that the stimulus is not the thing that is used as the main influence in perception, but the characteristics of the other person who provides the.

Personal Factors

What influences a person's perception is based on the experience that is passed as well as the understanding that is owned. In this personal factor, there are several factors that influence it, which include experience, motivation, and personality.

Situational Factors

A person will be judged by the first word he utters, and that first word will affect the next judgment, this theory is called the primacy effect. Jalaludin Rakhmat in his book entitled Communication Psychology mentions situational factors that can influence perceptions where these factors are proxemic clue, kinesic clue, face guide, paralinguistic clue, and artifactual clue.

Structural Factors

This factor is an external factor within an individual that can influence one's perception. These external factors, for example, are the environment and also culture.

According to Thorson and Powell (cited in Maharani, 2022) sense of humor is a person's way of responding to and coping with stress in their daily lives. In another study, Thorson and Powell (cited in Septiana, 2017) said that in the sense of humor there are 4 aspects that are multidimensional, namely; (1) Humor production; (2) Social use of humor; (3) Attitude towards humor; and (4) Use of humor as coping mechanism.

Ramandji (in Sari, 2021) mentions that there are several main functions of humor, which include; (1) To nourish the body; (2) To reduce stress level; (3) As a means of education; and (4) As a means of interpersonal communication.

METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach method. Qualitative research is research conducted to analyze the quality of relationships, situations, activities, or materials that are described holistically (Fraenkel, Wallen, and Hyun, 2012). Qualitative research will be heavily influenced by personal reflection, knowledge, social background, creativity, and personal abilities of researchers because qualitative research is interpretive (Raco, 2010). This research applied a purposive sampling technique to determine the data sources to be obtained. Fraenkel, Wallen, and Hyun (2012) state that this purposive sampling technique is a technique used to determine research informants based on the criteria of the researcher to determine compatibility with the research. Based on this theory, this research determines informants based on the criteria that have been made where a school located in one of the big cities in Indonesia is selected based on the school's explanation because the English teacher who teaches in the class is considered closer to the students. There were 18 informants who were willing to be interviewed. However, after being confirmed again, only 4 informants were willing to be interviewed, one informant was female and three others were male. The ages of the 4 informants ranged in age from 17 to 18 years old.

Table 1. Characteristic of Informants

Informants	Ages (years old)	Gender
PN-AP3	17	Male
PN-AK4	17	Male
PN-AP6	18	Male
PN-AK8	17	Male

There are several instruments used in this study which are used based on existing theories which include:

Main Instrument

The main instrument in qualitative research is the researcher himself (Murdiyanto, 2020). To conduct qualitative research, researchers are required to have knowledge of theories related to the matter to be studied.

The form of the interview instrument

The question and answer dialogue activity carried out between researchers and informants is called an interview (Siyoto and Sodik, 2015). In practice, this interview was conducted by prioritizing freedom of answer from the informant and also the interviewer may ask questions freely without following the guidelines of the question sheet that has been prepared.

Form of documentation instrument

The form of the documentation instrument can be divided into two, namely documentation guidelines which are made by containing outlines and check-lists which contain a list of variables for which data will later be collected Siyoto and Sodik (2015) This research used documentation as one of the instruments which are records of events, field conditions, and so on.

The purpose of the interview is to find out what the research subjects are thinking or their views on something (Fraenkel, Wallen, and Hyun, 2012). Humans are the main instrument in conducting interviews. Because the data obtained in the interview must be in the form of verbal. In this study, researchers used a structured and open interview model using Whatsapp as the medium. The data analysis technique used in this study is thematic analysis. According to Boyatzis, Braun and Clarke (in Heriyanto, 2018) states that thematic data analysis techniques can be used to identify patterns or codes that aim to get themes based on the data researchers get. In the same journal, Holoway and Todres (2003) said that thematic data analysis techniques are the foundation or basis for analyzing qualitative data. Furthermore Boyatzis (in Alhojailan and Ibrahim, 2012), said that the data illustrated in the thematic data analysis can be very detailed and relate to various subjects with their interpretations.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Types and How is the Humor Given in EFL classroom

Based on the students's answers, the types and how is the humor given by the teacher are interact using humor and teacher in the delivery of humor

Figure 1. Types and How is the Humor Given

Interact Using Humor

Based on the answers obtained from research informants, it were found that class that uses humor as an interaction tool are enough to provide positive benefits for the continuity of teaching and learning activities. Not only that, it turns out that interactions with humor have effects where these effects provide closeness and improve the quality of cooperation between teachers and students. This teacher and student intimacy was expressed by all informants, which their answers were: "mr. W always gives useful and funny knowledge. even though we're already home f when we talk to him again, he always teaches us how to speak English, every time we ask anything even though it's not important, Mr. W always answers in English, so we also learn how to speak English and listen" (PN-AP3) "According to the lesson, through the usual questions and answers" (PN-AK4)

"...so my teacher gave the correction by laughing together" (PN-AP6)

"usually because the material given/delivered is interesting so the students also give feedback with "practice" about the text/things being taught, sometimes accents or answers..." (PN-AK8)

The position of the teacher in the delivery of humor

From the interview, the teacher's position in humor is a very interesting answer because all informants answered things that had the same meaning. All informants gave answers about the teacher's role in humor in the class which showed that the English teacher in the class gave the same thing over and over again and all of these informants told the exact same thing. The answers they gave are described below:

The role of the teacher in provoking humor

After analyzing the transcription of the interview, as many as two informants out of four informants who answered the teacher as a source of humor explained that the teacher who teaches English often gives "bait" so that students interact with each other to create humor. The following are the answers collected from the informants:

"... what a funny thing that was the answer..." (PN-AP3)

"...about the text/things being taught, sometimes the accent or answers when students answer can be a separate joke/humor in class" (PN-AK8)

There is one unique answer from one of the informants. This informant gave the answer that the teacher becomes a person who plays the role of provoking anxiety which as a result of the anxiety caused, the class will become boisterous with laughter. The person explained that a student is asked a question about the material being studied, however, the teacher will make the student who is asked the question nervous so that the nervousness will provoke laughter from the other classmates. The following are the answers from the informant:

"But it's funny how nervous he is. Usually he also laughs when his friends laugh" (PN-AK4)

2) The role of teacher in the appreciation of humor

According to one informant this explained that the teacher only appreciated, not enjoyed the humor given.

The following are the answers from the informant:

"... because the one who did it at first was his friends, then the teacher only replied by laughing, but that doesn't mean he's laughing at the student, but it's like he's talking to himself (they have nonsense behaviour)" (PN-AP6)

Student's Perception of the Teacher's Sense of Humor When Learning in EFL Classroom

Based on the students's answers, the student's perception of teacher humor in EFL classroom is humor efficiency, teacher's ability on humor, the negative impact of using humor, and the impact of teacher humor on students.

Figure 2. Students' perception of teacher humor

The effectiveness of humor in the classroom

All informants who had been asked questions answered that there was the effectiveness of giving humor while learning English. It is believed to be able to have a positive effect on the ongoing learning activities and learning English in the classroom. There were two different themes from the answers given by the informants, namely humor has effectiveness as a regulator of a conducive classroom climate and humor can improve students' cognitive abilities when learning English. Here is the explanation:

Humor to improve students' cognitive abilities

Two informants mentioned that they got a positive influence from giving humor in the English classroom. They are able to remember study material easily and can also encourage themselves when they are going to study together with their English teacher. And here are the answers given by two informants:

“if the teacher is cool, I can easily understand the lesson, if he is not cool, I might understand, but if you study with him, would make you feeling lazy” (PN-AP3)

“the positive benefits/impacts of humor given by the teacher during class learning, in my opinion, create familiarity between the teacher and students which also facilitates the interaction of questions and answers on the material provided, because students perceive the teacher as a "cool" teacher, if you occasionally give a joke there is no need joking too often so as to stay safe in class, as well as improve the memorizing aspect of the material provided as well” (PN-AK8)

Humor can affect the classroom climate

The class that uses humor will certainly have a positive influence on the ongoing teaching and learning activities. Two informants gave answers that were themed into humor which had an influence on a conducive classroom climate. They explained that humor can encourage them to interact in class so as to make English learning classes not boring and make students could socialize with other students. The following are the answers from the informants:

“Because there are cool friends in it, not being a loner” (PN-AK4)

“learning becomes more fun and not boring” (PN-AP6)

Teacher's ability to limit the humor

According to three informants, a teacher must still have limits in providing humor in the classroom. This aims not to hurt the student's day or reduce the desire to learn. Furthermore, it turns out that teachers also have limitations in appreciating humor, namely by not causing laughter on their faces but also not giving the impression of anger. Not only that, it turns out that teachers who provide humor with high intensity are actually able to make their students lose respect for their teacher which of course will make their students' behavior not in accordance with what is desired.

Limit humor by reducing intensity

They explained that high-intensity humor was enough to make the class not conducive so that students' concentration on the material being taught was difficult to understand and they tended to ignore the assignments given by the teacher. The following are the answers from the informants:

“Because the nature of that person who has stepped on maturity knows what is the difference between too much joking understandable joke, especially in place like school/class...” (PN-AP6)

“so far there is nothing (negative effect of humor), other than for example the joke is too much the students demeaning teacher and neglect the assignments given” (PN-AK8)

Limited appreciation of humor

Appreciation of humor is an effective way to show that someone responds to or enjoys the humor presented and laughter is one way to appreciate humor. Because it might hurt the teacher to not give his appreciation of humor. The following is a student's answer of limiting the appreciation of humor:

“if you don't exceed the limit, just know manners” (PN-AP3)

Limiting humorous material

Not all types of humor can be enjoyed by everyone. There are several types of humor that are actually restricted in public places. A teacher still has to pay attention to the humor that is thrown in the classroom. Not only so that all students accept the humor, but also so that the humor does not cause quite complicated conflicts, especially if the conflict is about the emotions and minds of the students. According to a informant, there is humorous material that should not be thrown in class while studying. Because this humor is humor that requires a human object as a source of humor which makes the object of humor unable to control itself against its weaknesses. These informants stated that this humor should not be normalized or this humor not thrown too often so that the object of this humor can still carry out teaching and learning activities smoothly in line with its weaknesses. The following are the answers from the informant:

“So far, the humor/jokes from the teacher, which in my opinion should not be normalized in class, is about the physical or weaknesses of the students, where maybe the teacher means that these students can specifically be aware of their weaknesses but in fact it is just a distraction for them, and instead of getting better this student actually became "relaxed" because he would get used to getting satire in the form of jokes/satire humor like that” (PN-AK8).

Teacher humor inefficiency

Several informants said that providing humor in the class should not be too frequent or too little in intensity. This aims not to waste study time so that students do not focus on their humor but remain focused on the learning objectives that are being carried out. The following is the answer presented by the informant: “...so that it doesn't disturb the conduciveness of learning and still have fun while studying / without coercion or excessive fear of the teacher” (PN-AK8)

In fact, the teacher's humor, which is meant to be entertainment in the classroom so that the class is not too monotonous, according to one informant, is more towards "prestige". The student answered that humor is valued as prestige by today's children. Here is the answer:

“...you know for sure right now because the world of social media is rampant, so it's very rare for children to interact so that humor is more prestige nowadays” (PN-AP6)

d. The impact of teacher humor on students

One informant gave an answer that was quite unique among the others. He said that the teacher who gave humor was seen as something temporary. Even this informant stated that he tended to ignore humor as something important and was taken seriously by this informant. Not caring about the humor given is their way of responding to humor. Here is the answer:

“...The teacher's words are always not taken seriously” (PN-AP6)

Regarding the responses from the informants about the teacher's humor when learning English in the classroom, they all thought positively, that the humor created by the teacher was a means to develop their ability to speak English. Their opinion is in line with the theory described by Partin (in Wamin, 2020) in which the use of humor in the classroom has suggestions that humor can function as planned and has a positive effect after providing humor because the majority of respondents gave answers according to theory.

Some of the informant think that the provision of humor in the classroom must be limited. Based on a statement written by Shafee et al (in Horace and Mosin, 2021) which states that there are four limitations of humor that should be thrown in the classroom, namely by packaging humor in a concise manner, not too excessive, humor that is thrown must be in line with the learning material, and humor that is thrown must be able to make students laugh. Therefore, the humor that occurs in the classroom cannot be separated from the teacher's role in bridging the humor

An informant thought that the teacher could provoke student anxiety so that the anxiety generated could provoke laughter from other students. This nervousness has been described by David Krech and Richard S. Crutchfield (in Shambodo, 2020) who state that humor can be created from several factors. One of the factors is the situation factor. Students who are asked by the teacher to answer questions will feel under pressure so that they will feel uneasy when they are under pressure. Because of that anxiety, the other students felt it was a humor in itself.

Appreciation for humor will appear when the humor is created and given. One informant stated that the teacher plays a role in the humor that is created in the classroom, including as an appreciation. Appreciation of humor shows the level of sensitivity of the teacher's humor to the humor presented by him or directed at him. Sense of humor is one aspect or point of view regarding the multidimensional nature of humor. As stated by Martin (in Septiana, 2017) states that there are 6 aspects that are multidimensional, namely humor appreciation, sense of playfulness, personal recognition of humor, use of humor as a medium for adaptation, the use of humor as a medium for socializing. Students who think that the teacher appreciates the humor they create certainly do not think that these aspects greatly affect the form of humor appreciation. The limitations included in giving humor were stated by one of the informants who stated that physical characteristics and deficiencies in students are things that should be avoided in giving humor in the classroom. According to the informant, someone's limitations are not humor that provides benefits. The use of humor in the classroom is to establish good communication between the teacher and his students.

However, humor that is not in accordance with the level of sensitivity of a person's humor will not provide benefits in terms of communication. In one answer, the informant said that if the teacher gives humor about his student's shortcomings, it is likely that the student will feel like a person who does not care about his shortcomings to be corrected immediately. This is inversely proportional to the theory put forward by Knowles (2021) which states that humor can function as a coping mechanism.

Two participants mentioned that there are other limitations in providing humor in the classroom. The limit is a limit on the amount of intensity that is done. The higher the intensity of humor given in the class, the better and worse the effect will be. The good effect is that the closeness between teachers and students is getting closer because of good communication and emotional closeness because of high humor. However, giving humor with high intensity can also cause problems, one of which is that students don't care about the assignments given by the teacher. Of course this is not what the teacher wants. As stated by Wamin (2020) that humor can attract the attention of students in the classroom. However, this excessive attention tends to have the effect that the teacher in the class prefers to share humor with him compared to teaching and learning activities. Other informants stated that humor should not be thrown too often in the classroom as a form of teacher professionalism at work. The informant said that the teacher should understand where to do humor so that he stays on the right track.

An informant stated that humor becomes inefficient when it is given too often while learning is in progress. The participants stated that the more humor was given, the more time wasted just for fun. Humor, which should be a tool to lighten the mood, will actually destroy the atmosphere because too much humor will make the class noisy so that it can disrupt teaching and learning activities in that class and other classes that feel disadvantaged. The informant stated that learning material was easier to process in his brain than material given without humor. Not only that, as said by all informants that humor can increase the level of interaction between teachers and students. The interaction was felt by them to be more efficient when using humor while learning English. As said by Ramandji (Sari, 2021) that humor can be used as a means for interpersonal communication.

Students become closer to their teachers if their closeness is mixed with humor in their interactions. Tyagita and Iriani (2018) stated that the familiarity and collaboration created between teachers and students will

encourage both of them to motivate themselves to continue to be creative and also provide benefits in the form of a deeper introduction to the character of their students. This is evidenced by research findings from informants' answers which state that they feel closer to their teachers when they interact using humor. However, the teacher must also pay attention to the humor given to his students according to the statement of a participant. Even so, students who are given humor by their teachers sometimes don't really care whether the humor can affect them or not. In closing, the humor given by the teacher must be limited so that the humor can function properly. Besides being able to make learning exciting, fun, and enjoyable, humor can also make classes scary for some students. Therefore the teacher's humor must also pay attention to the conditions of the students, the atmosphere, and the material that will be used as material for making humor.

Giving humor makes people who are targeted to receive humor feel more positive thinking so that it brings positive benefits as well. The humor that occurs in the classroom occurs because the elements that influence the creation of humor have been fulfilled. Good humor can make the recipient of humor feel good feelings. The form of laughter from people who are targeted to receive humor is a form that the person needs entertainment to reduce the level of thinking fatigue. So that when giving humor is done, there are two possibilities that will occur, namely the recipient of humor will give his appreciation of humor by showing his laughter or the recipient of humor will feel that the humor given is inappropriate so that it brings facial expressions that describe feelings of emotion, not laughter.

Along with the development of an increasingly modern era, humor also experienced its own development. More and more teachers who plan to provide humor in their learning classes need to think carefully about plans for providing humor so that the humor given becomes useful humor. But even so, there is also humor that occurs spontaneously which is created according to the circumstances surrounding the giver and receiver of humor. Givers and recipients of humor also have their own subjectivity regarding their assessment of these humors. That way, even though humor has positive benefits for the recipient of humor, the humor giver still has a stake in considering the humorous material that will be given to the humor recipient.

CONCLUSION

After conducting data analysis, several points were found that could be concluded in this study. Which of these are:

Classroom interaction is more frequent

A good teacher is a teacher who can get closer to their students. Due to the difference in generations, the relationship between teacher and student is a bit distant. However, that does not mean that the relationship between a teacher and student cannot be applied. The relationship can be strengthened even in an unusual way, by using humor. In fact, teachers can identify the character of their students by frequently interacting with humor. As a result of recognizing the character of their students, it will be easy for the teacher to determine how to deliver material to their students so that students can easily process the material provided by their teacher knowing the traits of efficacious EFL teachers based on the students' insight, every EFL teacher is expected to follow and pay attention to those traits that can make them an efficacious person in teaching English. On the other hand, EFL teachers are expected to avoid the attitudes that can categorize them into inefficacious English teachers.

Besides that, for the students themselves, the humor that the teacher throws can also make them understand what to do in class. They can get positive results from using humor in the classroom. Students can also prioritize respect for teachers because if the relationship between teacher and student is well established, of course students will feel they need their teacher so that students have limits on what can be done and what is not allowed. Done to the teacher

Conducive classroom climate

A conducive classroom climate will make it comfortable for all teaching elements and the objects being taught. Because a conducive classroom climate greatly influences the process and learning outcomes. The ability to remember students will be easier to use when students feel comfortable while in class. So

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that making students comfortable in the classroom is one way to make the process and student learning outcomes better.

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